

Deep Learning-Based Multidimensional Item Response Theory Model for Mild Cognitive Impairment Patients' Digital Therapeutics: Model Development and Validation Study

Minjeong Kim, Dohyoung Rim*
Rowan Corporation, Seoul, Republic of Korea
dhrim@rowan.kr

Abstract

Background: Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) an early stage of cognitive decline that may precede dementia, characterized by noticeable reductions in cognitive function. MCI patients require cognitive training as part of effective intervention strategies to prevent dementia. Recently, digital therapeutics (DTx) have emerged as a promising approach for managing MCI providing accessible and data-driven cognitive training solutions. The efficacy of these interventions is significantly enhanced when tailored to individual cognitive profiles. It highlights the importance of systems that predict patients' DTx performance and recommend targeted interventions based on cognitive functions in diverse domains.

Objective: This study aimed to develop and validate a deep learning-based multidimensional item response theory (MIRT) model to predict personalized DTx scores in accordance with cognitive functions for patients with MCI.

Methods: MIRT allows for multidimensional assessment of patients' cognitive functions delicately based on item characteristics. Cyclic Dual Latent Discoverer (CDLD) excels at analyzing latent relationships within data. By combining these strengths, the CDLD-MIRT model provides a comprehensive framework for precise cognitive assessment and enhanced understanding of underlying patterns. To validate the model's accuracy, we conducted two experiments using clinical and simulated data. The clinical dataset comprised 60,541 records from 130 MCI patients aged 60-85 collected by 17 centers. These patients participated in a 24-week intervention, generating DTx performance scores. Each content item in the DTx was associated with two of five cognitive functions: executive function, attention, memory, visuospatial skills, and language/calculation. We compared the proposed CDLD-MIRT model against MIRT, Deep-IRT, and CDLD models, evaluating accuracy using root mean square error (RMSE). Additionally, an indirect experiment with simulated data was performed to verify whether the model predicts scores according to domain-specific cognitive functions. This experiment assessed the accuracy of the model in estimating latent cognitive abilities, employing correlation coefficients as evaluation metrics.

Results: In the simulated data, CDLD-MIRT demonstrated an RMSE of 0.0980, surpassing MIRT (0.2949), Deep-IRT (0.2276), and CDLD (0.1169). In clinical data, CDLD-MIRT achieved an RMSE of 0.1017, compared to MIRT (0.2477), Deep-IRT (0.1217), and CDLD (0.1021). In indirect experiment, the average Pearson correlation is 0.8539, and Spearman Correlation is 0.8786.

Conclusions: We integrated deep learning with MIRT to enhance the accuracy of DTx performance assessments across different domains. The proposed CDLD-MIRT model demonstrates higher accuracy compared to other models without rigid probabilistic assumptions unlike traditional IRT models. Moreover, based on the indirect experiment, the model accurately predicts patient scores in alignment with their cognitive functions. This approach facilitates a precise evaluation of cognitive abilities and supports customized item selection. Moreover, it holds the potential to enable personalized therapeutic interventions for MCI patients, as well as to support the self-assessment of DTx tools.

Trial Registration: Trial Registration ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT05023057

Keywords: mild cognitive impairment; dementia; digital therapeutics; multidimensional item response theory; deep learning; predictive model; cognitive training; tailored medicine

Introduction

Mild Cognitive Impairment and Digital Therapeutics

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) represents an intermediate stage between normal aging and dementia, characterized by impaired cognitive functions that, however, do not significantly affect daily activities [1]. Given the high likelihood of MCI progressing to dementia, early detection and appropriate treatment are essential for slowing cognitive decline [2]. Both pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches are available to prevent the progression of MCI to dementia [3]. Cognitive training, a non-pharmacological approach, is increasingly recognized as a method to prevent dementia and treat MCI by improving cognitive function and maintaining daily living abilities in patients, with fewer side effects than medications [4, 5].

Digital therapeutics (DTx) emerge as an optimal vehicle as non-pharmacological cognitive interventions. These evidence-based software solutions provide structured cognitive training that adapts to individual needs by incorporating advanced artificial intelligence (AI) [6, 7]. The DTx with AI targets specific cognitive functions affected in MCI while providing performance tracking and personalized prescription based on precise prediction. This combination can ensure standardized delivery, improved adherence, and objective measurement of cognitive outcomes [8]. Moreover, personalized training yields superior outcomes compared to conventional training programs, simultaneously improving mood and reducing caregiver burden [9].

The Superbrain program, developed by Rowan in South Korea, exemplifies DTx to cognitive intervention targeting MCI patients to prevent dementia [10]. Grounded in the comprehensive framework of the Seoul Neuropsychological Screening Battery [11], the program strategically addresses five key cognitive functions: executive function (EXE), attention (ATT), memory (MEM), visuospatial (VISUO), and language/calculation (LANG/CAL). It consists of a suite of cognitive training game items specifically designed to simultaneously target two cognitive functions—designated as the primary cognitive function (PCF) and the secondary cognitive function (SCF)—from among the five key areas.

Cyclic Dual Latent Discovery AI Model

To enhance its effectiveness, Superbrain incorporates an AI model, Cyclic Dual Latent Discovery (CDLD) [12]. The CDLD is a deep learning (DL) model designed to extract latent traits from two interacting entities to predict a target outcome. It consists of two neural networks, the discoverer and predictor. The discoverer identifies latent traits of each entity through a cyclic training mechanism that iteratively refines their representations. These latent traits are then passed to the predictor network, which leverages them to generate accurate predictions of the target variable.

The CDLD integrated into the Superbrain program the interaction between two entities: the user (individuals with MCI) and the item (DTx game). By analyzing latent traits based on the user's cognitive state and the inherent properties of each DTx item, CDLD enables a fine-grained understanding of user-item dynamics. This allows the system to accurately predict user performance after engaging with DTx item.

Multidimensional Item Response Theory

To enhance the precision of cognitive assessment focusing on individual cognitive functions specifically in Superbrain DTx, we propose the integration of multidimensional item response theory (MIRT) into CDLD.

MIRT is an advanced extension of item response theory (IRT), offering a sophisticated approach to evaluating multiple cognitive abilities through analysis of users' responses in the field of psychometrics [13]. While IRT conceptualizes the measured cognitive function as a unidimensional construct, MIRT

allows for a more nuanced understanding by simultaneously modeling multiple latent traits that contribute to test performance. It can capture the complex, interconnected nature of cognitive functioning. MIRT is to model the probability of a user correctly answering an item based on their underlying cognitive abilities and specific item traits such as difficulty and discrimination [14]. By systematically examining users and items interactions, MIRT provides a robust methodology for estimating individual cognitive capabilities and item traits in the observed sample pool. MIRT models range from 1-parameter to 3-parameter structures, our research specifically employs the 2-parameter model to balance computational complexity with comprehensive cognitive assessment.

Key parameters in the 2-parameter MIRT framework include:

- θ (theta): the user's ability parameter
- b : the item's difficulty parameter
- a : the item's discrimination parameter

These parameters collectively enable precise estimation of a user's performance level. The probability that a user with an ability parameter θ correctly answers an item characterized by a difficulty parameter b and discrimination parameter a is represented by this model, which reflects the interaction between these critical factors.

MIRT models are categorized into compensatory and non-compensatory types. In compensatory models, high ability in one cognitive dimension can compensate for lower abilities in another. Non-compensatory models, by contrast, consider each dimension as contributing independently, without any compensatory effects [15].

For this study, we employed a compensatory MIRT model to analyze the Superbrain DTx game item. It is because the item was designed with the understanding that five key cognitive functions are not entirely independent. The mathematical formulation of the compensatory MIRT model is presented in Formula 1.

$$P(X_{ij} = 1 | \theta_j, a_i, d_i) = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\exp(a_{ik} \cdot \theta_{jk} - b_i)}{1.0 + \exp(a_{ik} \cdot \theta_{jk} - b_i)} \quad (1)$$

where:

- P is the probability that user j correctly answers item i .
- X_{ij} is the observed response of user j to item i .
- $a_i = (a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{ik})$ is the vector of item discrimination parameters for item i .
- b_i is the vector of difficulty parameter for item i . Higher values indicate more challenging items.
- $\theta_j = (\theta_{j1}, \theta_{j2}, \dots, \theta_{jk})$ is the vector of trait parameters for person j .
- k is the index of the dimensions representing the cognitive abilities, with m indicating the total number.

This approach recognizing the interconnected nature of cognitive functions aligns well with CDLD, which can capture these relationships with sophisticated precision. Consequently, we integrated CDLD with MIRT to develop CDLD-MIRT. Given that each Superbrain DTx item was designed to assess two cognitive functions, we employed a modified version of the MIRT equation as presented in Formula 2.

$$P(X_{ij} = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\{-(a_{i1} \cdot \theta_{j1} + a_{i2} \cdot \theta_{j2} - b_i)\}} \quad (2)$$

where:

- a_{i1}, a_{i2} : The discrimination parameters for the two cognitive dimensions related to item i .
- θ_{j1}, θ_{j2} : The abilities of user j in the two cognitive dimensions.

Comparison Model

We developed CDLD-MIRT, a new model integrating CDLD with MIRT. Since no other models combining DL and MIRT currently exist for direct comparison, we established a comprehensive evaluation framework using three alternative approaches: standard MIRT implementations [16] (without deep learning capabilities), Deep-IRT [17] (which combines DL with unidimensional IRT), and original CDLD (without integrating with MIRT). These enable an indirect evaluation of the proposed model's effectiveness as a MIRT-based DL framework, in the context of DTx for cognitive evaluation and intervention.

Additional Simulation Study for Indirect Validation of Cognitive Domain-Specific

Assessment

Given the lack of directly comparable baseline models, we conducted an additional simulation study to indirectly validate the effectiveness of CDLD-MIRT in assessing domain-specific cognitive abilities. The primary objective of this study is to recommend appropriate DTx for individuals with MCI based on their cognitive profiles. We hypothesize that if the model can quantitatively evaluate domain-specific cognitive abilities—through the multidimensional θ estimates derived from MIRT—it will meaningfully contribute to this clinical goal. To test this, we slightly modified the original experimental settings to allow comparison with reference cognitive traits embedded in our simulated dataset, as detailed in the Methods section. This approach enables us to examine whether the model accurately captures individuals' cognitive strengths and weaknesses, thereby providing further evidence of its utility for DTx-guided cognitive assessment.

In summary, this research is going to develop and validate a clinical prediction model, CDLD-MIRT, by comparing it with other DL and MIRT models to experimentally confirm whether this approach achieves higher accuracy, ultimately proposing a model suitable for DTx applications.

Methods

Real Data

Data Source and Description

The study investigated the efficacy of a 24-week between May 2018 and December 2020, multimodal intervention for MCI in adults aged 60-85 years [10]. Participants were recruited based on having at least one dementia risk factor, including hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidemia, obesity (BMI ≥ 25 kg/m²), abdominal obesity (waist circumference ≥ 90 cm for men, ≥ 85 cm for women), metabolic syndrome, smoking, education level ≤ 9 years, insufficient physical activity compared to WHO guidelines for older adults (less than 150 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic exercise weekly or less than 75 minutes of high-intensity aerobic exercise weekly), or insufficient social activity. Additional inclusion criteria were: self-reported or caregiver-reported cognitive decline; objective impairment (≥ 1.0 SD below age/education-adjusted norms) in at least one cognitive function (delayed verbal/visual memory recall, executive function, naming, visuospatial construction, or attention); preserved activities of daily living; K-MMSE score above "mean-1.5 SD" (age/education-adjusted); ability to use a tablet PC independently or with assistance; presence of a knowledgeable caregiver; and provision of written informed consent.

Participants were excluded if they presented with any of the following: psychiatric disorders such as major depression; dementia; other neurodegenerative diseases including Parkinson's disease; malignant tumors within the past 5 years without complete remission; vascular reconstruction or stent procedures within the past year; severe or unstable symptomatic cardiovascular disease; other severe or unstable physical conditions (including acute and severe asthma, active peptic ulcer, severe liver disease, kidney disease requiring dialysis, or any other medical condition that might interfere with study completion); severe visual impairment, hearing loss, or communication disorders that would

prevent intervention implementation or efficacy evaluation; illiteracy; clinical laboratory findings potentially related to cognitive decline (e.g., significant thyroid dysfunction, vitamin B12 or folate deficiency, neurosyphilis); investigator assessment that the participant might not cooperate throughout the study or could not safely participate in interventions such as exercise; or concurrent participation in other intervention studies. Withdrawal criteria included investigator determination that continued participation would harm the participant's welfare, participant withdrawal of consent, or investigator judgment that withdrawal would be in the participant's best interest for any reason

Dataset Description and Preprocessing

This paper utilized data derived from a clinical study, in which participants with MCI engaged with training games in Superbrain designed to enhance these cognitive functions. During the trial, the real dataset was generated, comprising 60,541 score records obtained from 130 MCI patients. They interacted with a total of 20 distinct types of games, each designed with levels ranging from 1 to 6-10, resulting in 166 unique items.

Each item was developed to train target cognitive function, PCF and SCF. The PCF represents the primary focus of training, while the SCF addresses additional cognitive function. For instance, consider the item "Sudoku", where the PCF is EXE and the SCF is ATT. Sudoku primarily aims to train EXE, requiring users to strategize and make decisions. Additionally, it enhances ATT, as users must maintain focus to avoid errors and successfully complete Sudoku [18, 19].

The maximum playtime for each item was set at three minutes, during which users aimed to play as many sets as possible. Scores were calculated by converting the number of correct sets into a percentage, with a maximum score of 100 points. For instance, if a user played four sets and solved three sets correctly, they received a score of 75. These scores were divided by 100 and set as target data for prediction and validation of all experimented models.

Given that users could play as many sets as they wanted within limited time, we consider that a user who solved 15 sets correctly may exhibit greater cognitive abilities than one who solved only 2 sets correctly, even if both achieved same score. To account for this, we first grouped scores by game type. Within each group, we normalized the number of played sets. We then divided the raw scores by 100 to convert them to a 0–1 scale and multiplied them by the normalized set counts. These weighted values allowed us to interpret the results as accuracy-like rates bounded between 0 and 1. As shown in Figure 1 (before adjustment), all items' score distributions are concentrated in the upper range (0.6–1.0), which could cause overfitting and the relationship between item difficulty and scores was not clearly observable. In contrast, Figure 2 (after adjustment) exhibits a more balanced distribution, where most scores gradually decrease as item difficulty increases, reflecting increasing difficulty. The number of outliers is also reduced, enhancing the interpretability of the scores as accuracy-like measures.

Figure 1. Before adjustment, accuracy distribution. The y-axis represents the scores, and the x-axis represents the item IDs. The game number on the right side of the figure corresponds to a specific game, with each game consisting of levels ranging from difficulty levels 6 to 10. Each specific level of a particular game represents a single item, resulting in a total of 166 items.

Figure 2. After adjustment, accuracy distribution. The y-axis represents the scores, and the x-axis represents the item IDs. The "Game ID" shown on the right side of the figure represents different types of games. Each ID corresponds to a specific game category, consisting of 6 to 10 items, and results in a total of 166 items.

To move to the next level, users were required to achieve a score above a certain threshold. If a user failed to reach the threshold within 3 minutes, progression to the next level was restricted. Additionally, some users may have chosen not to interact with certain items, resulting in datasets where individual users have multiple score records for the same item or, conversely, no records at all. To manage the varying nature of score data, Deep-IRT and MIRT models do not process multiple scores directly. Therefore, we averaged the scores for the same item type completed by the same user to create a singular data point for analysis. In contrast, the CDLD and CDLD-MIRT models are capable of effectively handling duplicate scores without the need for averaging.

Simulated Data

To enhance generalization and diversity, we constructed simulated data in accordance with widely accepted virtual IRT experimental designs [14, 20]. The simulated dataset comprised 100 users and 100 items, resulting in a total of 10,000 data points. PCF and SCF data were randomly assigned to each item across five cognitive functions equally 2000. The parameters θ_1 , θ_2 (ability), b (difficulty), and a_1 , a_2 (discrimination) were randomly generated from specific statistical distributions. The θ values were sampled from a standard normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The b values were drawn from a truncated normal distribution, also with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1 but truncated between -3 and 3. The a values were derived from a truncated log normal distribution with a mean of 1 and a standard deviation of 0.5, truncated between 0 and 2 (Figure 3). Response accuracies were calculated by applying these parameter values to the MIRT formula (Formula 2), and used as target value for validation of models. Simulated data game score distribution is shown in Figure 4. Both datasets were shuffled and divided into training, validation, and test sets using an 8:1:1 ratio.

Figure 3. Generated theta, a, and b parameter distribution of simulated data.

Figure 4. Simulated data game score distribution. The y-axis represents the scores, and the x-axis represents the item IDs.

CDLD-MIRT Model Architecture and Training process

Figure 6. User latent discoverer. Only user latent is updatable, while item latent (denoted by gray) is fixed during training. User latent traits (θ_{EXE} , and θ_{ATT}) are selected through the cognitive function layer according to the corresponding item and trained based on the MIRT formula.

Figure 5. Only the user latent discoverer network is trained.

Figure 6. The opposite setting, where only the item latent discoverer network is trained.

Figure 7. The predictor uses the latent traits obtained from the discoverer to predict target values based on the MIRT formula.

Figure 8. Overall CDLD-MIRT architecture, discoverers and predictor

CDLD-MIRT is a newly proposed deep neural network (DNN) model, integrates CDLD and MIRT methodologies. The proposed model is based on the CDLD structure. Unlike original CDLD, which assigns each user and each item a single 32-dimensional latent trait, CDLD-MIRT allows users to have five marked 32-dimensional latent traits— θ_{EXE} , θ_{ATT} , θ_{MEM} , θ_{VISUO} , and $\theta_{LANG/CAL}$ —each stored in a layer corresponding to the cognitive functions. Additionally, CDLD-MIRT sets three latent traits for each item, symbolized as a_1 , a_2 , and b .

When the model trains the score data for a user interacts with item, for example the item Sudoku's PCF is EXE and the SCF is ATT, the model gets θ_{EXE} trait from user and sets to the DNN_{PCF} (a DNN designed to process PCF traits) and θ_{ATT} to the DNN_{SCF} (a DNN designed to process SCF traits). Each item's designated PCF and SCF determine which user latent traits (θ) are passed through. After these processes, the 32-dimensional latent traits are transformed into a 1-dimensional output, representing the user's cognitive level as PCF and SCF when engaging with the DTx item.

Each DTx item is assigned three 32-dimensional item latent traits: a_1 , representing the discrimination parameter for PCF; a_2 , representing the discrimination parameter for SCF; and b , representing the difficulty parameter of the item. Item latent traits, a_1 , a_2 , and b , assigned to each item piece are input into their respective DNNs for processing and ultimately result in a 1-dimensional output. For example, in the Sudoku, the user trait θ_{EXE} after passing through DNN_{PCF} is multiplied by a_1 , which has passed DNN_{a1} ; similarly, θ_{ATT} after passing DNN_{SCF} is multiplied by a_2 , which is passed through DNN_{a2} . The sum of these is then subtracted by b , which has passed DNN_b , and the result is passed through a sigmoid function. This forms the basis of the compensatory MIRT model, as formalized in Formula 4.

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\{DNN_{a1}(a_{1i}) \cdot DNN_{PCF}(\theta_{ji1}) + DNN_{a2}(a_{2i}) \cdot DNN_{SCF}(\theta_{ji2}) - DNN_b(b_i)\}}} \quad (3)$$

where:

- the user's cognitive function latent traits θ_1 and θ_2 are fed into the deep neural networks DNN_{PCF} and DNN_{SCF} , which capture primary and secondary cognitive functions, respectively.
- a_{1i} and a_{2i} are the vector in the 32-dimension of item i , representing the discrimination parameter for the PCF and SCF, respectively.
- b_i is the vector in the 32-dimension of the difficulty parameter of the item i .

The training process alternates between user latent discoverer model and item latent discoverer model, based on the CDLD cyclic framework. When the user latent traits are being trained, the item latent traits are kept fixed, and vice versa. (Figure 5, 6) While training user traits, the DNN_{PCF} and DNN_{SCF} , the layer containing the five latent traits is also updated. This approach is based on the premise that item design should prioritize a PCF and a SCF, while also recognizing that cognitive functions are not entirely independent and frequently interact in complex ways [21]. It aims to reflect the brain's intricate cognitive structure. By updating multiple cognitive functions simultaneously, the model may more effectively capture the intricate relationships among these functions, offering a more realistic representation of how cognitive processes are activated and trained in practical scenarios. Furthermore, this method aligns well with the compensatory nature of the MIRT model.

The predictor model generates predictions based on the MIRT formula, utilizing five user latent traits and three item latent traits derived from the discoverer model. Consistent with the discoverer, the predictor retrieves the appropriate user latent traits corresponding to the PCF and SCF assigned to each DTx item via the cognitive function layer. These selected traits are then used in the MIRT equation (Formula 4), which serves as the final activation function for prediction (Figure 7). The predictor focuses on accurately estimating predictions using these latent traits.

Figure 8 illustrates the overall architecture of the proposed CDLD-MIRT model.

Comparison Model

MIRT in RStan

In this study, we implemented the MIRT model in RStan to conduct a comparative analysis regarding MIRT performance. RStan is an R package that interfaces with Stan, a platform for statistical modeling and Bayesian inference using Markov Chain Monte Carlo method [16]. Since RStan cannot directly handle multiple accuracy data, we used average weighted accuracy across repeated interactions for each unique user-item combination. The final implementation of the model utilized MIRT formulation presented in Formula 2.

Deep-IRT

To validate the applicability of CDLD-MIRT as a MIRT-based model for DTx, we selected Deep-IRT as a comparative model. It is one of the promising models combining DL and 1-parameter IRT, that has been widely used as an alternative to traditional IRT methods in psychometrics. To better accommodate real data, we made additional modifications to the model's implementation based on experimental results. As previously described, the real data contained multiple instances of the same user playing the same DTx item, resulting in repeated weighted accuracy for identical user-item pairs. To address this redundancy, we calculated the average for each unique user-item pair and used this value in subsequent analyses. The original Deep-IRT model includes a mechanism for assigning different weights to users and items, using threshold-based grouping with accuracy thresholds set at 0.8 for high-performing groups and 0.2 for low-performing groups. We modified this mechanism to better fit our real and simulated data characteristics after conducting two experiments to determine the optimal grouping strategy for weight assignment. In the first approach, we assigned users with weighted accuracy greater than 0.8 to the high-performance group and those with accuracy less than 0.2 to the low-performance group. Items were grouped using the same fixed thresholds. In the second approach, we ranked users by their weighted accuracy and divided them into the top 20% and bottom 80%, applying the same percentile-based grouping to items as well. Comparative experiments showed that the second method—based on percentile ranking—yielded higher prediction accuracy in both simulated and real-world settings. As a result, we adopted this approach in our implementation. The final predictions were generated using the same IRT formulation as in the original model, as defined in Formula 4.

$$P(X_{jk} = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\{-(\theta_j - b_i)\}} \quad (4)$$

where:

- P is the probability that user j correctly answers item i .
- θ_j : The abilities of user j in one cognitive dimension.
- b_i : The difficulty parameter for item i .

Simulation Study Using Unidimensional Theta

Although cognitive abilities are not directly measurable—which is why we initially modeled cognitive functions as 32-dimensional latent traits—we aimed to validate whether our model can accurately capture the cognitive domains of MCI patients. To achieve this, we restructured our setting by simplifying the five cognitive function latent traits (theta) into unidimensional traits, allowing us to explicitly verify the model's interpretability and correctness.

This validation is feasible with simulated data, as the randomized theta values provide known ground truth. To support this experiment, we modified the DNN architecture by incorporating L2 kernel regularization, applying batch normalization, and reducing the depth of the neural network layers. By translating these 1-dimensional latent traits, we examined whether the model successfully captures the cognitive functions of MCI patients.

Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was assessed using the root mean square error (RMSE) as the primary metric. RMSE offers a clear measure of prediction accuracy by computing the square root of the average squared differences between predicted and actual values. The comparative analysis included both simulated and clinical datasets to evaluate CDLD-MIRT against MIRT implemented in RStan, Deep-IRT, and CDLD. This comparison used probability estimates from the IRT model, with the test data RMSE serving as the benchmark for predictive accuracy across all models.

In the indirect simulation test, we evaluated the user latent traits, represented as unidimensional theta values, using both Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients. Since cognitive functions

represent relative rather than absolute abilities, correlation measures were selected as they effectively capture the relative relationships between predicted and actual cognitive traits.

Ethics Statement

This study has received approval from multiple Institutional Review Boards (IRBs), including Inha University Hospital (INHAUH-2021-06-040), Ewha Women’s University Seoul Hospital (SEUMC-2021-07-037), Ewha Women’s University Mokdong Hospital (EUMC-2021-08-003), Ajou University Hospital (AJIRB-BMR-SUR-21-323), Bobath Memorial Hospital (P01-202109-11-002), Dong-A University Hospital (DAUHIRB-21-168), Chonnam National University Hospital (CNUH-2021-326), Hanyang University Hospital (HYUH-2021-07-041), Myongji Hospital (MJH-2021-08-032), Jeonbuk National University Hospital (CUH-2021-08-043), Pusan National University Hospital (2108-016-015), Konkuk University Hospital (KUMC-2021-08-023), Samsung Medical Center (SMC-2021-08-022), CHA Bundang Medical Center (CHAMC-2022-01-020), Catholic Kwandong University International St. Mary’s Hospital (IS22EIMI0008), Daejeon Eulji Medical Center (EMC-2021-12-004), and Uijeongbu St. Mary’s Hospital (UIRB-2022-0428).

Results

Simulated Data

The accuracy of the four models using simulated data is summarized in Table 1 as RMSE values. Compared to CDLD-MIRT, the traditional MIRT model showed a 66.77% higher RMSE, followed by Deep-IRT with a 56.96% increase, and the original CDLD model with a 16.23% increase.

Clinical Data

The RMSE values for each model using actual clinical data are presented in Table 1. The CDLD-MIRT model achieved a substantially lower RMSE, showing improvements of 58.95% over MIRT, 16.45% over Deep-IRT, and 0.39% over CDLD. These results demonstrate the robustness of CDLD-MIRT in modeling real-world cognitive performance with greater precision than previous approaches.

Table 1. RMSE values for each model using simulated and clinical data.

	Simulated Data	Clinical Data
MIRT		
	0.2949	0.2477
Deep-IRT		
	0.2276	0.1217
CDLD		
	0.1169	0.1021
CDLD-MIRT		
	0.0980	0.1017

Result of Simulation Study Using Unidimensional Theta

As shown in Figure 9 and Table 2, the five theta parameters exhibit very high correlations, with an average Pearson correlation of 0.8539 and Spearman correlation of 0.8786. Although the primary objective of CDLD-MIRT is to predict DTx scores, these strong correlation values indicate that the model’s predictions are based on accurate estimations of cognitive functions.

Figure 9. Scatter plot comparing discovered cognitive functions with actual cognitive functions in the simulated dataset. The x-axis represents the actual rank, which refers to the ground-truth ranking in the simulated dataset. The y-axis shows the discovered rank, which represents the model-estimated ranking based on the unidimensional-latent variables learned by the model. Each point corresponds to an individual in the dataset, and the dashed line represents the ideal one-to-one correspondence between the actual and discovered rankings.

Table 2. Correlation values among the five cognitive domain theta parameters.

	Pearson Correlation	Spearman Correlation
θ_{EXE}	0.8597	0.9009
θ_{ATT}	0.7549	0.7986
θ_{MEM}	0.8920	0.9168
θ_{VISUO}	0.8938	0.8908
$\theta_{\text{LANG/CAL}}$	0.8690	0.8857

Discussion

Principal Findings

Figure 10. Conceptual overview of our goal using the CDLD-MIRT model. (A) Each MCI patient possesses unique, domain-specific cognitive functions. (B) Patients engage with DTx programs and generate performance scores. (C) CDLD-MIRT utilizes these score data to predict patient outcomes. (D) By transforming user latent traits into unidimensional representations, the model enables personalized assessments of domain-specific cognitive abilities and has the potential to recommend individualized DTx interventions in the future.

Despite significant advancements in DTx and applications of AI, there are few instances where models like CDLD, which predict patient DTx scores for prescriptions, have been implemented. While the original CDLD model can evaluate only a single cognitive domain, our proposed CDLD-MIRT model expands this capability, enabling comprehensive assessments across five distinct cognitive functions. Rather than treating cognition as a broad, CDLD-MIRT enables granular evaluation and the delivery of personalized interventions tailored to specific cognitive domains in need of improvement. As a result, the model enables more accurate predictions of patient performance in DTx and supports domain-specific therapeutic recommendations (Figure 10). This is especially critical for MCI patients, who often exhibit heterogeneous patterns of cognitive impairment that necessitate focused interventions targeting specific cognitive domains for effective dementia prevention [22].

Furthermore, this multidimensionality can make it broad applicable not only to MCI but also to other DTx contexts, where it will help evaluate diverse functional profiles and impairments within a single disease category, ultimately informing more tailored prescription decisions. This improved assessment capability allows for tailored treatment recommendations, representing a step toward more precise, individualized DTx prescriptions.

The CDLD-MIRT model not only achieves higher prediction accuracy but also leverages the robust theoretical framework of MIRT framework; a psychometrically established methodology widely recognized in psychological measurement. By integrating predictive modeling CDLD-MIRT, this approach provides a more reliable method for evaluating patients' cognitive abilities and DTx characteristics, thereby enhancing both the theoretical robustness and practical utility of diagnostic assessments in DTx. Furthermore, this study pioneers the new MIRT methodology, moving away from conventional MIRT methods by leveraging DL. It moves beyond traditional probabilistic assumptions of normal distribution unlike other MIRT models, and enhances by capturing complex, non-linear relationships. As a result, it enables the development of a more flexible and credible model, unconstrained by rigid statistical assumptions, and better suited for real-world clinical applications.

Limitations and Further Research Direction

Our model has several limitations. First, while our current study was based on data from completed clinical trials, we are interested in exploring the use of our model with a broader range of DTx programs and more diverse datasets, including real-time data collected from ongoing interventions. We believe that testing the model in such settings could offer deeper insights and enhance its practical relevance.

Additionally, while the concept of Time-Integrated IRT already exists, we would also like to explore incorporating it into our framework, as it may further strengthen our approach [23].

Second, we have not yet compared our model with any MIRT combined with DL, limiting our ability to assess performance and accuracy directly. Given the diverse types of models within MIRT and the potential for expansion through DL, we plan to conduct comparative experiments as new research emerges in this area. Finally, while this study utilized only simulated data in indirect experiment, we aim to apply our model to real-world datasets to evaluate the actual cognitive functions of MCI patients. In future research, we plan to conduct cognitive assessments and investigate whether the CDLD-MIRT model can accurately capture patients' cognitive abilities based on real cognitive test results.

Conclusions

The CDLD-MIRT model demonstrates superior performance over other models by providing detailed assessments across five cognitive domains. By integrating deep learning with the robust psychometric foundation of MIRT, our model enables more accurate predictions of patient performance in DTx and has potential to support personalized, domain-specific intervention strategies. These advancements position CDLD-MIRT as a flexible and reliable framework well-positioned to improve diagnostic precision and optimize DTx prescriptions across a wider range of therapeutic contexts.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by Korea Dementia Research Project through the Korea Dementia Research Center (KDRC), funded by the Korea government (Ministry of Health & Welfare and MSIT), Grant/Award Number: RS-2021-KH112062, RS-2021-KH112636 and RS-2024-00337993; National Research Council of Science and Technology (NST) Aging Convergence Research Center by the Korea government (MSIT), Grant/Award Number: CRC22013-600; Institute of Information and Communications Technology Planning and Evaluation (IITP) by the Korea government (MSIT), Grant/Award Number: 2022-0-00448/RS-2022-II220448; and Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) by the Korea government (MSIT), Grant/Award Number: NRF-2020M3E5D2A01084721. The study's funders had no role in the study design, data collection, analysis, interpretation of data, writing of the report, or decision to submit the article for publication.

Authors' Contributions

MJK contributed to conceptualization, methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing-original draft, writing-review&editing, and visualization. DHR contributed to software, validation, investigation, resources, data curation, writing-review&editing, visualization, supervision, project administration, and funding acquisition. JHJ, SYM, YKP, CHH, JJ, HRN, and SHCho contributed to investigation, resources, data curation, writing-review&editing, project administration, and funding acquisition. SHChoi contributed to investigation, resources, data curation, writing-review&editing, supervision, project administration, and funding acquisition.

Conflicts of Interest

None declared

Abbreviations

AI: artificial intelligence

ATT: attention

CDLD: Cyclic Dual Latent Discoverer

DL: deep learning

DNN: deep neural network
DTx: digital therapeutics
EXE: executive function
IRT: item response theory
LANG/CAL: language/calculation
MCI: mild cognitive impairment
MEM: memory
MIRT: multidimensional item response theory
PCF: primary cognitive function
RMSE: root mean square error
SCF: secondary cognitive function
VISUO: visuospatial

References

1. Gauthier S, Reisberg B, Zaudig M, Petersen RC, Ritchie K, Broich K, et al. Mild cognitive impairment. *Lancet*. 2006 Apr 15;367(9518):1262-70. [doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(06)68542-5] [Medline: 16631882]
2. Langa KM, Levine DA. The diagnosis and management of mild cognitive impairment: a clinical review. *Jama*. 2014 Dec 17;312(23):2551-61. [doi: 10.1001/jama.2014.13806] [Medline: 25514304]
3. Chen YX, Liang N, Li XL, Yang SH, Wang YP, Shi NN. Diagnosis and Treatment for Mild Cognitive Impairment: A Systematic Review of Clinical Practice Guidelines and Consensus Statements. *Front Neurol*. 2021;12:719849. [doi: 10.3389/fneur.2021.719849] [Medline: 34712197]
4. Lissek V, Suchan B. Preventing dementia? Interventional approaches in mild cognitive impairment. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2021 Mar;122:143-64. [doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2020.12.022] [Medline: 33440197]
5. Mowszowski L, Batchelor J, Naismith SL. Early intervention for cognitive decline: can cognitive training be used as a selective prevention technique? *International Psychogeriatrics*. 2010;22(4):537-48. [doi: 10.1017/S1041610209991748]
6. Sverdlov O, Van Dam J, Hannesdottir K, Thornton-Wells T. Digital therapeutics: an integral component of digital innovation in drug development. *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics*. 2018;104(1):72-80. [doi: 10.1002/cpt.1036] [Medline: 29377057]
7. Hong JS, Wasden C, Han DH. Introduction of digital therapeutics. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*. 2021 2021/09/01/;209:106319. [doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2021.106319] [Medline: 34364181]
8. Palanica A, Docktor MJ, Lieberman M, Fossat Y. The need for artificial intelligence in digital therapeutics. *Digital biomarkers*. 2020;4(1):21-5. [doi: 10.1159/000506861] [Medline: 32399513]
9. Bahar-Fuchs A, Webb S, Bartsch L, Clare L, Rebok G, Cherbuin N, et al. Tailored and adaptive computerized cognitive training in older adults at risk for dementia: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*. 2017;60(3):889-911. [doi: 10.3233/JAD-170404] [Medline: 28922158]
10. Cho SH, Kang HJ, Park YK, Moon SY, Hong CH, Na HR, et al. SoUth Korean study to PrEvent cognitive impaiRment and protect BRAIN health through Multidomain interventions via facE-to-facE and video communication plaTforms in mild cognitive impairment (SUPERBRAIN-MEET): Protocol for a Multicenter Randomized Controlled Trial. *Dement Neurocogn Disord*. 2024 Jan;23(1):30-43. [doi: 10.12779/dnd.2024.23.1.30] [Medline: 38362052]
11. Kang Y, Na D, Hahn S. Seoul neuropsychological screening battery. Incheon: Human brain research & consulting co. 2003. [doi: 10.12779/dnd.2023.22.1.1] [Medline: 36814700]
12. Rim D, Nuriev S, Hong Y. Cyclic Training of Dual Deep Neural Networks for Discovering User and Item Latent Traits in Recommendation Systems. *IEEE Access*. 2025. [doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3526270]

13. Ackerman T. Graphical representation of multidimensional item response theory analyses. *Applied psychological measurement*. 1996;20(4):311-29. [doi: 10.1177/014662169602000402]
14. Embretson SE, Reise SP. *Item response theory*: Psychology Press; 2013. ISBN: 1410605264. [doi: 10.4324/9781410605269]
15. Reckase MD. 18 Multidimensional Item Response Theory. *Handbook of statistics*. 2006;26:607-42. [doi: 10.1016/S0169-7161(06)26018-8]
16. Carpenter B, Gelman A, Hoffman MD, Lee D, Goodrich B, Betancourt M, et al. Stan: A probabilistic programming language. *Journal of statistical software*. 2017;76. [doi: 10.3390/electronics10091020]
17. Tsutsumi E, Kinoshita R, Ueno M. Deep item response theory as a novel test theory based on deep learning. *Electronics*. 2021;10(9):1020. [doi: 10.18637/jss.v076.i01]
18. Ashlesh P, Deepak KK, Preet KK. Role of prefrontal cortex during Sudoku task: fNIRS study. *Translational neuroscience*. 2020;11(1):419-27. [doi: 10.1515/tnsci-2020-0147] [Medline: 33335780]
19. Bargagliotti LA. Resolving one problem in a 10-star Sudoku puzzle. *Nursing Education Perspectives*. 2006;27(2):62-109. [doi: 10.1214/aoms/1177706645]
20. Box GE, Muller ME. A note on the generation of random normal deviates. *The annals of mathematical statistics*. 1958;29(2):610-1. [doi: 10.31887/DCNS.2019.21.3/pharvey] [Medline: 31749647]
21. Harvey PD. Domains of cognition and their assessment. *Dialogues in clinical neuroscience*. 2019;21(3):227-37.
22. Bahar-Fuchs A, Webb S, Bartsch L, Clare L, Rebok G, Cherbuin N, et al. Tailored and Adaptive Computerized Cognitive Training in Older Adults at Risk for Dementia: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2017;60(3):889-911. [doi: 10.3233/jad-170404] [Medline: 28922158]
23. Su Y, Cheng Z, Luo P, Wu J, Zhang L, Liu Q, et al. Time-and-concept enhanced deep multidimensional item response theory for interpretable knowledge tracing. *Knowledge-Based Systems*. 2021;218:106819. [doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2021.106819]